

Electronic and Infrared Spectral Characteristics of Alizarin Maroon Complexes of Al(III), As(III) and As(V)

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The complexes of alizarin maroon with Al(III), As(III) and As(V) have been investigated. The stoichiometry, structure and stability of the complexes have been characterised using the electronic and infrared spectral measurements. The results indicate the probable formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates (metal-ligand). The values of $\log \beta$ for the different complexes have been determined.

ALTHOUGH alizarin maroon (3-amino-1,2-dihydroxyanthraquinone) is readily functionable as dyestuff and as histological reagent, few investigations have been made about its chelating characteristics and the stability of its metal chelates^{1,2}. In this note, preparation and characterisation of the solid chelates of alizarin maroon with Al^{3+} , As^{3+} and As^{5+} and their stability constants in solution are reported.

Solutions ($10^{-2}M$) of Al^{3+} , As^{3+} and As^{5+} were prepared using the Analar products of aluminium nitrate, sodium arsenite and sodium arsenate respectively, by dissolving the requisite weight of the salt in twice distilled water, in presence of a small quantity of HNO_3 or $HClO_4$ acid to prevent hydrolysis. Alizarin maroon (AZM) solution ($10^{-3}M$) was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount of the reagent (BDH) in redistilled water. Buffer solutions consisting of boric acid, borax, succinic acid and sodium sulphate of pH 3-9 were prepared as given by Britton³.

The absorption spectra of solutions were measured on a unicam S.P. 500 spectrophotometer. The IR spectra of the organic ligand as well as those of the solid chelates were recorded as KBr-discs on a Beckman infrared spectrophotometer. Conductometric titrations were carried out using a Pye conductance bridge and a dip-type conductivity cell.

Spectrophotometric measurements : In a previous study⁴ it was found that the spectral behaviour of AZM is influenced by the pH of solutions. It seems therefore necessary to look for a medium suitable for the colour development of its complexes with Al^{3+} , As^{3+} and As^{5+} . Thiel buffer solutions are found to be the most suitable media. It was found that the maximum colour development is attained at pH 5.4 for As(III), 5.8 for the As(V) and 8.0 for the Al(III) complexes. In the visible region, the Al^{3+} -AZM complex exhibits $\lambda_{max} \sim 570$ nm. The band shows an increase in intensity and an apparent

red shift (to ~ 595 nm) with increasing the concentration of either AZM or the metal ions. The spectra of the complexed ligand with As^{3+} or As^{5+} possess an absorption band with λ_{max} near 620 nm. The obvious red shift of the bands in comparison with that characterising the free ligand⁴ at the same pH verify the complex formation with metal ions.

On maintaining the concentration of AZM constant and changing the metal ion concentration, the absorbance value increases in a linear manner over a range of 6.25×10^{-5} to $10^{-3}M$ of metal ion. The linear variation together with the high values of ϵ_{max} denote that AZM can be utilised for the determination of small quantities of the metal ions under investigation.

The composition of the complexes formed in solution was examined by the molar ratio⁵, straight line⁶, continuous variation⁷, slope ratio⁸ and the limiting logarithmic⁹ methods. The results obtained indicate the probable formation of two types of complexes with stoichiometric ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) for the three metal ions investigated.

The apparent stability constants of the complexes formed were calculated from the measurements and were as follows : Al^{3+} ($\log \beta_1 = 4.61$, $\log \beta_2 = 9.53$), As^{3+} ($\log \beta_1 = 4.18$, $\log \beta_2 = 8.65$) and As^{5+} ($\log \beta_1 = 4.23$, $\log \beta_2 = 8.84$). The values indicate that the complexes exhibit moderate stability and can be arranged according to their stability in the following order :

The conductance-molar ratio curves are characterised by well defined breaks denoting the probable formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 types of complexes with the metal ions. The plots of the specific conductivity vs the volume of the complexing agent added to the metal ion solutions show gradual increase in conductance indicating that hydrogen ions are liberated

from the ligand through bonding with the metal ion.

I.R. Spectra of Solid Chelates :

Generally, the spectra of all complexes of the reagent studied with Al(III), As(III) and As(V) exhibit bands in the vicinity of 3400 cm^{-1} which denote the assignment of ν_{OH} . The bands become broadened, less intense and suffer a frequency shift when the ligand is bonded with the metal ion. The spectra of the metal chelates show an overlap of the bonded $\text{W}_{\text{C=O}}$ with $\text{W}_{\text{C=C}}$ near 1600 cm^{-1} and a red shift is observed. This indicates that the quinone structure is influenced by the substituent. The bands observed at 1460 , 1270 and 1200 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of AZM assigned to δ_{OH} , δ_{CH} and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ respectively. The bands at 1460 and 1270 cm^{-1} suffer a red shift on complexation of the ligand with the metal ions investigated. The intensity of the band on the higher frequency side decreases apparently due to the proton displacement from the $\alpha\text{-OH}$ group on complex formation. From the foregoing results as well as those obtained from the

elemental analysis of the solid chelates we can propose that chelate formation takes place through the C=O and the $\alpha\text{-OH}$ group and leads to proton displacement.

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